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Differentiating long QT syndrome genotypes using electrocardiographic geometric parameterization and machine learning approaches

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E-mail: srutova.martina@seznam.cz, Lenka.Lhotska@cvut.cz and vaclav.kremen@cvut.cz**Keywords:** long QT syndrome, LQTS discrimination, electrocardiogram parameterization, electrocardiogram classification, cardiovascular diseases, support vector machine classificationSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Long QT Syndrome (LQTS) is an inherited cardiac disorder characterized by dysfunctional cardiac ion channels, which result in prolonged QT intervals on electrocardiograms (ECGs). LQTS can lead to severe clinical manifestations, including syncope, ventricular arrhythmias, and sudden cardiac death. Effective genotype-specific management strategies are essential to mitigate the risk of life-threatening arrhythmias. This study aims to achieve automatic discrimination among the LQT1, LQT2, and LQT3 genotypes to enable targeted treatment and prevention strategies. Utilizing ECG data from the Telemetric and Holter ECG Warehouse's LQTS database, our methodology involves an automated extraction process of short ECG signals, geometric parameterization techniques, and classification using a two-stage cascade of binary support vector machine classifiers. The input features for the classifiers are derived from Lead I ECG signals sampled at 200 Hz, highlighting the potential application in developing single-lead ECG monitoring devices and applications, such as widely used smartwatches, for which short recording duration, low sampling frequency, and arm-to-arm lead measurements are fundamental prerequisites for practical use. The proposed classifier achieved 71% weighted accuracy on out-of-sample data (LQT1: 65% recall, 58% precision; LQT2: 79% recall, 82% precision; and LQT3: 71% recall, 77% precision). Our findings demonstrate the feasibility of noninvasive genotype differentiation for LQTS based on the morphological analysis of ECG signals, providing an advancement in the field of personalized cardiology and the development of portable diagnostic tools.

1. Introduction

Long QT syndrome (LQTS) is a cardiac disease within the genetic channelopathies group, characterized by prolonged ventricular repolarization and an increased risk of life-threatening arrhythmias. Its prevalence is roughly 1 in 2000 to 2500 (Schwartz *et al* 2001), with variable penetrance influenced by diverse inherited and acquired factors (Abrams and MacRae 2014). Electrocardiogram (ECG) abnormalities, especially the prolongation of the QT interval and certain patterns in the ST-T wave segment (Zhang *et al* 2000), are caused by abnormalities in potassium or sodium

channels, even though QT prolongation is multifactorial and influenced by autonomic tone, medication, and electrolyte balance.

The three major genotypic subtypes of long QT syndrome (LQT1, LQT2, and LQT3) differ in their underlying ion-channel dysfunctions and typical triggering conditions. LQT1 events often occur during exercise, particularly swimming; LQT2 is commonly precipitated by emotional or auditory stimuli; and LQT3 episodes tend to arise during rest or sleep (Moss *et al* 1999, Schwartz *et al* 2001, Khositseth *et al* 2004). Together, these genotype-specific trigger profiles underscore the complexity of clinical management

and personalized risk assessment. Therapeutic strategies therefore range from β -blocker therapy to implantation of cardioverter-defibrillators in high-risk individuals (Shimizu and Antzelevitch 2000, Rohatgi et al 2017). Accurate genotype identification is essential for tailored risk stratification and treatment (Goldenberg et al 2008, Zareba and Cygankiewicz 2008, Schwartz et al 2012). Although genetic testing remains the definitive diagnostic method, its use may be constrained by availability, cost, and turnaround time.

Current research on LQTS is detailed in a summary study (Tardo et al 2023), which provides a comprehensive overview of related LQTS publications. The core focus of LQTS studies, using ECG analytics and prediction, includes distinguishing between healthy controls and congenital LQTS patients, identifying concealed LQTS in individuals with normal QT intervals, differentiating between genotypes, and exploring the relationship between ECG morphology and risk stratification. The used parameters encompass time intervals, T-wave morphology markers, and measurements derived from vector cardiography.

Existing works often rely on 12-lead ECGs, higher sampling rates, and complex deep learning models with limited interpretability and higher compute, limiting portability to wearables. Our work targets single-lead, 200 Hz data with interpretable geometric features.

This study aims to improve the accessibility of genotype differentiation through ECG signal processing and machine-learning methods. Several other recent works have also demonstrated the potential of machine learning and deep learning approaches in detecting LQTS (Hermans et al 2020, Bos et al 2021, Prifti et al 2021, Aufiero et al 2022, Doldi et al 2022, Draelos et al 2022). We reflected on the studies that outline the differentiation of LQTS patients from non-affected individuals and those with borderline QT intervals (Tardo et al 2023). We proceed from our previous study (Srutova et al 2025), which presented the successful application of novel geometrical approaches for the LQT3 distinction. Current work shows how the previously proposed methods (Srutova et al 2025) can be used to distinguish between the three main genotypes LQT1, LQT2, and LQT3. This could facilitate risk stratification and disease management. Its importance will increase with the development of genotypic therapy (Schwartz et al 1995, Compton et al 1996, Tan et al 2006).

2. Methods

2.1. Data set and signal preparation

We utilized the Genotyped Long QT Syndrome E-HOL-03-0480-013 database (Couderc 2010), an extensive Holter ECG repository from the Telemetric and Holter ECG Warehouse (THEW). It provides

long-term ECG signals with genetic data from LQTS patients. The database includes 246 records for LQT1, 145 for LQT2, and 35 for LQT3, with approximately 17–18 h for each signal record sampled at 200 Hz. We restricted analysis to Lead I to emulate single-lead wearable devices.

The signal selection strategy was intended to emulate short-term resting ECG acquisition conditions, focusing on capturing stable and consistently observable ECG characteristics, regardless of potential loss of information describing waveform alternans. We selected daytime segments records between 10 a.m. and 8 p.m., assuming patient vigilance during these hours; however, daytime rest or naps although daytime rest or naps cannot be absolutely ruled out (figure 3). The 25% of each record with the lowest LF/HF heart rate variability (HRV) parameter (Malik et al 1996), indicating rest, was used. This parameter was employed for automated signal segment selection, as it is commonly considered an indicator of sympathovagal balance; however, it does not represent a strict physiological assumption. The LF/HF ratio was computed using the PhysioNet Cardiovascular Signal Toolbox (Goldberger et al 2000, Vest et al 2018) in 200-beat sections with a 100-beat offset. From these sections, the central 60 ECG beats from the most extended vigilance resting periods were pre-processed and delineated using the algorithms from PhysioNet (Goldberger et al 2000) and ECGdeli (Pilia et al 2021) toolboxes. Primarily, the PhysioNet delineation was used, with ECGdeli as a backup. Critical positions, such as the beginnings, peaks, and ends of individual waves of each ECG cycle, were automatically identified and marked (figure 1).

Signals from individuals with multiple genotypes identified, or other genetic mutations that were also part of the database, were excluded. The signals underwent partial visualization to assess quality (figure 1). Any signals that were noisy or unsuccessfully delineated were also excluded. Delineation challenges included atypical ECG morphologies, such as flat, biphasic or notched T-waves. High-quality, short vigil resting ECG sections of 60 beats duration were extracted for each record, pre-processed, and prepared for the automatic machine learning approach. The final dataset comprised three genotype-specific groups: 205 records for LQT1, 86 records for LQT2, and 31 records for LQT3. One-third of the signals from each group were randomly selected to create an out-of-sample testing dataset for validating the final machine-learning model.

2.2. Feature extraction

We calculated twenty parameters (Srutova et al 2025) describing the ST-T region of the ECG signal. They were derived from traditionally used ECG features that detail the duration and amplitude of the ST and T-wave segments. Additionally, we introduced two

innovative geometric parameterization approaches: the transformation to the unit circle and the area under the curve, as detailed in our previous LQTS research (Srutova *et al* 2025). For this study, we highlight four parameters (figure 2) that we identified as the most informative for the differentiating LQTS genotype:

- (1) $tDurationUp$ (figure 2 - first line): This traditional time feature describes the duration between the onset of the T-wave (T_{on}) and the peak of the T-wave (T_{peak}). (Srutova *et al* 2025)

Geometric Parameters via Unit Circle Transformation: Transformation to the unit circle (figure 2 - third line) is a normalization technique that maps the ECG signal, represented by the function $f(t)$, to coordinates $[X, Y]$ on the unit circle by scaling time and amplitude. Mathematically, this transformation for a wave beginning at

t_{ON} , peaking at t_{PEAK} , and ending at t_{END} can be described as:

For the ascending part of the wave

$$\text{Time scaling } X = -1 + \frac{t - t_{ON}}{t_{PEAK} - t_{ON}}$$

$$t \in \langle t_{ON}, t_{PEAK} \rangle$$

$$\text{Amplitude scaling } Y = \frac{f(t) - f(t_{ON})}{f(t_{PEAK}) - f(t_{ON})}$$

$$t \in \langle t_{ON}, t_{PEAK} \rangle$$

For the descending part of the wave

$$\text{Time scaling } X = \frac{t - t_{PEAK}}{t_{END} - t_{PEAK}}$$

$$t \in (t_{PEAK}, t_{END})$$

Figure 2. Visualization of foundational features used for the LQTS classification, and transformation of the related parts of the ECG waves into the unit circle. The first column shows the ST-T segment of the ECG signal in the time domain. The bolded part of the signal is transformed into the unit circle (the second column). The creation of parameter *tDurationUp* (blue) is described in the first line, *tAreaUpc* (green) and *tAreaDownc* (gray) in the second line, *oneAreaUp* (red) in the third line, and *oneSTTArcUp* (yellow) *oneAreaDown* (blue) in the fourth line.

$$\text{Amplitude scaling } Y = \frac{f(t) - f(t_{END})}{f(t_{PEAK}) - f(t_{END})}$$

$$t \in (t_{PEAK}, t_{END})$$

In this transformation, the beginning of the ECG wave aligns with the coordinates $[-1,0]$, the peak with $[0,1]$ (for both positive and negative waves), and the end with $[1,0]$. Time and amplitude scales are uniformly adjusted to facilitate independent waveform comparisons.

(2) *oneAreaUp* (figure 2 - third line): After transforming the T-wave to the unit circle, this parameter calculates the area from the onset to

the peak of the transformed T-wave using the rectangle method of integration. The value of this parameter is always positive. (Srutova et al 2025). The parameter expresses the area under the ascending part of the T-wave transformed into a unit circle.

(3) *ratioSTTUpDown-perc*: This value is calculated as the ratio of *oneSTTArcUp* (figure 2 - fourth line) to *oneAreaDown* (figure 2 - fourth line) described as follows. (Srutova et al 2025).

The ECG section, formed by the ST segment and T-wave together, is transformed to the unit circle. The feature *oneSTTArcUp* corresponds to the integral of the area under the ascending part

of this section and the parameter *oneAreaDown* corresponds analogously to the integral of the area of the descending part of this section. (Srutova et al 2025). The parameter expresses the ratio between the area under the ascending and descending parts of the ST-T segment transformed into a unit circle.

The last feature used in this study is derived from method of calculation of the area under the ECG curve.

- (4) *tAreaUpDownRatio*: This is the ratio of *tAreaUpc* (figure 2 - second line) to *tAreaDownc* (figure 2 - second line). (Srutova et al 2025)

The feature *tAreaUpc*: is the area under the ECG signal (for a positive T-wave) or above it (for a negative T-wave), linked to the onset (T_{on}) and peak (T_{peak}) of the T-wave. The ECG is set on the baseline so amplitude values are adjusted such that the amplitude at T_{on} is zero. Any ECG values below the amplitude at T_{on} are considered zero for a positive T-wave (or above for a negative T-wave). The integral is computed using the rectangle method starting at the peak point. The parameter assumes positive values for positive T-waves and negative values for negative T-waves. The *tAreaDownc* is calculated similarly to *tAreaUpc*, but the boundary values are peak (T_{peak}) and the end (T_{end}) of the T-wave. The parameter also assumes positive values for positive T-waves and negative values for negative T-waves. (Srutova et al 2025)

Due to the identical polarity of the areas in the ratio, the resulting value of the parameter *tAreaUpDownRatio* was always positive.

These extracted features, particularly the geometric parameters derived from the unit circle transformation, provide robust metrics for classifying LQTS genotypes using machine learning approaches.

2.3. Statistical analysis and classification model

We used a statistical approach with machine learning to identify key ECG features for distinguishing LQTS genotypes. A two-stage binary classifier cascade was employed, first differentiating LQT2 from the LQT1 and LQT3 groups, then separating LQT1 and LQT3. This stepwise refinement maximized the discriminative power of the selected ECG features.

Classifier for LQT2 Genotype Separation:

Given the non-Gaussian distribution of the features, we employed the Wilcoxon rank-sum test to filter and rank the most relevant features. This nonparametric test assesses the null hypothesis that two independent samples originate from the same distribution. To enhance the robustness of our feature selection, we balanced the input data to approximate a 1:1:1 ratio for the LQT1, LQT2, and LQT3 genotypes. Specifically, the balanced dataset included the complete LQT1 set once, the LQT2 set twice, and the

LQT3 set seven times. We compared the differences between the LQT2 genotype and the other two at a 5% significance level.

To the original unbalanced training dataset, we applied the Spearman rank correlation coefficient with a threshold of 0.6 to remove features that were highly correlated and thus offered limited additional informational value, while still preserving features that carried useful discriminative information despite showing moderate inter-feature correlation. This nonparametric measure evaluates the strength and direction of a monotonic relationship between two continuous or ordinal variables, ensuring that the selected features are mutually uncorrelated.

Ultimately, we identified three uncorrelated features with the highest discriminatory power for distinguishing the LQT2 group from the combined LQT1 and LQT3 groups. These features were used as input variables for the classification model.

The binary Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier was trained using the selected features, with parameters optimized via a Gaussian kernel function. To account for the varying number of patients across different LQTS genotypes, we assigned weights to the training data vectors, with values set to 1 for LQT1, 2.4 for LQT2, and 6.5 for LQT3. The classifier was trained and cross-validated using a 5-fold cross-validation technique on the training dataset, which consisted of 137 LQT1, 58 LQT2, and 21 LQT3 patients. This approach allowed us to identify the most effective model for classifying the LQT2 genotype.

Classifier to Distinguish Between LQT1 and LQT3 Genotypes:

To identify appropriate parameters for distinguishing between LQT1 and LQT3 genotypes, we conducted statistical analyses on these two groups. Using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test, we ranked parameters based on their discriminatory potential between LQT1 and LQT3, applying a 5% significance level.

We minimized mutual correlation among parameters by calculating the Spearman correlation coefficient for each pair, applying an absolute threshold of 0.6. We identified three best uncorrelated parameters with the highest discriminatory power as input variables for the model.

We trained the binary SVM classifier using only data from LQT1 and LQT3 patients in the training dataset. The model's parameters were optimized using a Gaussian kernel function. To account for the imbalance in patient numbers between these genotypes, we weighted the training data vectors, setting the weights to 1 for LQT1 patients and 6.5 for LQT3 patients. The classifier was trained and cross-validated using a 5-fold cross-validation technique on the training dataset, which consisted of 137 LQT1 and 21 LQT3 patients. This approach identified the best-performing model for distinguishing between these genotypes.

While more complex models such as neural networks are widely used in machine learning, their internal decision processes can be more difficult to interpret, which may limit their practical transparency in applications where model explainability is important. Given these considerations, SVMs were selected for this study due to their transparency, interpretability, fast training times, and high accuracy. SVMs are particularly effective with smaller datasets, providing robust performance with relatively low computational demands. These characteristics make them especially well-suited for the scope of our analysis. The suitability of the model choice was validated within the MATLAB programming environment. The model was trained using the MATLAB Classification Learner App, with automatically optimized hyperparameters: *Kernel Scale* ($KS = 1.3$) and *Box Constraint* ($C = 1$).

A complete overview of the LQTS genotype classifier development process is provided in figure 3.

2.4. Classifier performance measurements

The proposed classifier's accuracy was verified using an independent out-of-sample test dataset (68 LQT1, 28 LQT2, 10 LQT3), comprising one-third of all analyzed signals. The division into training and testing datasets was random and non-stratified. To address the imbalance in the testing dataset, the classifier outputs were weighted as follows: 1 for LQT1, 2.4 for LQT2, and 6.8 for LQT3.

3. Results

Through the design and evaluation of twenty candidate parameters, our statistical analysis identified three critical features for each classifier within the cascade, effectively distinguishing between the LQT1, LQT2, and LQT3 genotypes. These features

predominantly describe the ST and T-wave segments of the ECG curve.

Classifier for LQT2 Genotype Separation:

The following parameters were identified as the most discriminative for the LQT2 genotype: *tDurationUp*, *oneAreaUp* and *ratioSTTUpDown-perc*.

Statistical analysis using the Wilcoxon rank-sum test revealed highly significant p-values (less than 0.001) for all three parameters. The concrete p-values were 2.46×10^{-10} for *tDurationUp*, 3.49×10^{-10} for *oneAreaUp*, and 3.11×10^{-10} for *ratioSTTUpDown-perc*. Additionally, the Spearman correlation coefficient confirmed the mutual independence of these features, with correlation values not exceeding the predetermined threshold of 0.6 (figure 4).

Classifier to Distinguish Between LQT1 and LQT3 Genotypes:

The statistical analyses identified the following parameters as the most effective for distinguishing between LQT1 and LQT3 genotypes: *tDurationUp*, *tAreaUpDownRatio* and *oneAreaUp*.

The Wilcoxon rank-sum test indicated highly significant p-values (less than 0.001) for all three parameters. The concrete p-values were 3.69×10^{-15} for *tDurationUp*, 1.92×10^{-11} for *tAreaUpDownRatio*, and 4.32×10^{-15} for *oneAreaUp*. The Spearman correlation coefficient corroborated the mutual independence of these features, with correlation values remaining below the threshold of 0.6 (figure 5).

The distributions of these critical features across the different genotypes are illustrated in figure 6.

Classifier Performance

Utilizing these selected parameters, the cascade of the two SVM classifiers, optimized with a Gaussian kernel function, demonstrated strong performance (figure 7). The classifiers achieved an overall accuracy of 71% on the out-of-sample testing data, representing a more than two-fold improvement over random selection:

LQT1 Group: Achieved a recall of 65% and a precision of 58%.

LQT2 Group: Demonstrated high sensitivity, with a precision of 82% and a recall of 79%.

LQT3 Group: Demonstrated strong classification performance, with a precision of 77% and a recall of 71%.

4. Discussion

The present study demonstrates that geometric ECG parameterization combined with a two-stage SVM classification structure can effectively discriminate among the three principal LQTS genotypes.

Our results show that the proposed geometric ECG parameterization techniques—particularly the unit-circle transformation—provide compact and highly interpretable descriptors of ST–T wave morphology. These findings are consistent with our earlier work (Srutova et al 2025), which focused primarily on distinguishing the LQT3 genotype and confirmed that the proposed geometric parameterization method capture clinically meaningful morphological differences. Building on these insights, the present study extends the applicability of this approach and

demonstrates effective discrimination among all three major LQTS genotypes (LQT1, LQT2, and LQT3), even when using single-lead ECGs sampled at 200 Hz. The method’s robustness across automatically identified resting segments further supports its suitability for brief clinic-style ECG recordings and potentially for implementation in wearable or low-power monitoring devices.

In this work, we identified three uncorrelated parameters that were most effective in distinguishing the LQT2 genotype from others: the time duration between the beginning and peak of the T-wave (*tDurationUp*), the area under the ascending part of the T-wave after transformation to the unit circle (*oneAreaUp*), and the ratio between the areas of the ascending and descending parts of the ST–T wave, also transformed to the unit circle (*ratioSTTUpDown-perc*).

For discriminating between LQT1 and LQT3 patients, the optimal feature set included *tDurationUp*, *oneAreaUp*, and the ratio between the areas of the ascending and descending parts of the T-wave in the time domain (*tAreacUpDownRatio*).

Our findings emphasize the significance of ST segment morphology and the ascending and descending

**Testing Data
(SVM model -Fine Gaussian)**

Predicted	LQT1	44 21.7%	12 5.9%	20 9.9%	57.9% 42.1%
	LQT2	12 5.9%	53 26.1%	0 0.0%	81.5% 18.5%
	LQT3	12 5.9%	2 1.0%	48 23.6%	77.4% 22.6%
		64.7% 35.3%	79.1% 20.9%	70.6% 29.4%	71.4% 28.6%
	LQT1	LQT2	LQT3	Actual	

Figure 7. Confusion matrix for the final cascade SVM classifier model used for LQTS genotype discrimination, tuned with a Gaussian kernel function. It represents results for the weighted out-of-sample testing dataset with the following weights: LQT1—1, LQT2—2.4, LQT3—6.8. Minor inaccuracies may arise from rounding. The independent out-of-sample test dataset includes 68 LQT1, 28 LQT2, and 10 LQT3 ECG records.

parts of the T-wave, along with their interrelationships, in determining LQTS genotypes.

Using these parameters, we developed a cascade of two SVM classification models optimized with a Gaussian kernel function. The first classifier distinguished the LQT2 group from the others, while the second classifier differentiated between LQT1 and

LQT3 genotypes. This cascade approach achieved an accuracy of 71% on the out-of-sample testing dataset, marking a significant improvement over random selection.

The main comparable study that provided a more complex LQTS genotypic differentiation was conducted by (Bos et al 2021), which utilized a

convolutional neural network (CNN) model trained on a database of 12-lead ECGs from 965 LQTS patients. Their testing dataset included 149 LQT1, 109 LQT2, and 32 LQT3 individuals. To ensure comparability of our results, we adjusted published (Bos *et al* 2021) testing confusion matrix (figure 8). We balanced the number of patients in each group to align with our methodology. Although our study demonstrated a reduced ability to differentiate LQT1 patients compared to the CNN model, it achieved a better balance between precision and recall for the LQT3 genotype.

A common challenge identified in both studies is the misclassification of approximately 10% of patients, who may carry the LQT3 genotype but are incorrectly identified as LQT1. This issue presents an opportunity for future research. Although we did not employ models as complex as those in the referenced study, which reported an accuracy of 74%, our approach yielded comparable results with an accuracy of 71%.

Our methodology prioritizes explainability and is particularly suited for single-channel applications with low sampling frequencies. Given these constraints, we consider our outcomes highly favorable and see significant potential for further research. We anticipate that incorporating data from additional ECG leads will enhance diagnostic accuracy.

4.1. Limitations

This study acknowledges several limitations. The limited number of LQT3 signals may have affected the robustness of our results. Even with class-weighting

during training, the small LQT3 sample constrains morphological variability, which can reduce generalizability for LQT3 and introduce a residual bias toward LQT1/LQT2 patterns. The study deliberately focused exclusively on Lead I signals, but incorporating additional leads might improve classification accuracy. While practical for smartwatch applications, this study's 200 Hz sampling frequency might miss ECG signal details. In addition, because THEW predominantly represents Western populations, ethnic and demographic ECG variability may limit generalizability, and external validation on ethnically diverse, multi-center cohorts is needed to ensure broader applicability.

The innovative automatic approach study may occur minor inaccuracies. They could be mitigated by manual methods, but at the expense of time and cost. Thus, a balance between efficiency and accuracy is crucial.

While providing good repeatability and scientifically recognized outputs, open-source toolboxes for ECG signal delineation may fail with atypical ECG waves. These morphological variations could be significant for distinguishing LQTS genotypes.

Additionally, the limited availability of genotyped ECG signals is a common constraint in LQTS research. Although the THEW database is among the largest in this field, the number of signals, particularly for the LQT3 genotype, remains low. This limitation was mitigated by weighting the input data when designing the classifier. However, the small sample size can still influence the variability of results

depending on the training and testing data split. Importantly, the proposed methods may help identify additional candidates for genetic testing and clinical follow-up, the gradual expansion of LQTS genotype-annotated databases.

Database expansion is anticipated with ongoing research in LQTS. Despite its limitations, this work represents a significant milestone for future studies due to its unique approach.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that a Support Vector Machine (SVM) model, utilizing geometrically parametrized morphological features, can meaningfully distinguish between Long QT Syndrome (LQTS) genotypes. Our approach is distinguished by its use of data from a highly accessible source: short, resting-state ECG signals from a single lead (Lead I, 200 Hz), typical of Holter monitoring. The success of this minimalist approach confirms its applicability for integration into common cardiology devices and emerging wearable technologies, eliminating the need for complex multi-lead systems or prolonged recordings.

By validating this novel parameterization technique, our findings underscore the transformative potential of machine learning in electrophysiology. This work represents a significant step toward developing automated, non-invasive diagnostic tools for LQTS. Such advancements can streamline clinical workflows, facilitate earlier and more accessible screening, and ultimately improve patient outcomes.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelectrocard.2010.07.015>.

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References

- Abrams D J and MacRae C A 2014 Long QT syndrome *Circulation* **129** 1524–9
- Aufero S, Bleijendaal H, Robyns T, Vandenberg B, Krijger C, Bezzina C, Zwinderman A H, Wilde A A M and Pinto Y M 2022 A deep learning approach identifies new ECG features in congenital long QT syndrome *BMC Med.* **20** 162
- Bos J M, Attia Z I, Albert D E, Noseworthy P A, Friedman P A and Ackerman M J 2021 Use of artificial intelligence and deep neural networks in evaluation of patients with electrocardiographically concealed long QT syndrome from the surface 12-lead electrocardiogram *JAMA Cardiol.* **6** 532–8
- Compton S J, Lux R L, Ramsey M R, Strellich K R, Sanguinetti M C, Green L S, Keating M T and Mason J W 1996 Genetically defined therapy of inherited long-QT syndrome *Circulation* **94** 1018–22
- Couderc J-P 2010 A unique digital electrocardiographic repository for the development of quantitative electrocardiography and cardiac safety: the Telemetric and Holter ECG Warehouse (THEW) *J. Electrocardiol.* **43** 595–600
- Doldi F et al 2022 Detection of patients with congenital and often concealed long-QT syndrome by novel deep learning models *J. Pers. Med.* **12** 1135
- Draeos R L, Ezekian J E, Zhuang F, Moya-Mendez M E, Zhang Z, Rosamilia M B, Manivannan P K R, Henao R and Landstrom A P 2022 GENESIS: gene-specific machine learning models for variants of uncertain significance found in catecholaminergic polymorphic ventricular tachycardia and long QT syndrome-associated genes *Circ. Arrhythm. Electrophysiol.* **15** e010326
- Goldberger A L, Amaral L A, Glass L, Hausdorff J M, Ivanov P C, Mark R G, Mietus J E, Moody G B, Peng C-K and Stanley H E 2000 PhysioBank, physiotoolkit, and PhysioNet: components of a new research resource for complex physiologic signals *Circulation* **101** e215–20
- Goldenberg I et al 2008 Long-QT syndrome after age 40 *Circulation* **117** 2192–201
- Hermans B J M et al 2020 Improving long QT syndrome diagnosis by a polynomial-based T-wave morphology characterization *Heart Rhythm* **17** 752–8
- Khositseth A, Tester D J, Will M L, Bell C M and Ackerman M J 2004 Identification of a common genetic substrate underlying postpartum cardiac events in congenital long QT

- syndrome *Heart Rhythm* **1** 60–4
- Malik M, Bigger J T, Camm A J, Kleiger R E, Malliani A, Moss A J and Schwartz P J 1996 Heart rate variability: standards of measurement, physiological interpretation, and clinical use *Eur. Heart J.* **17** 354–81
- Moss A J et al 1999 Comparison of clinical and genetic variables of cardiac events associated with loud noise versus swimming among subjects with the long QT syndrome *Am. J. Cardiol.* **84** 876–9
- Pilia N, Nagel C, Lenis G, Becker S, Dössel O and Loewe A 2021 ECGdeli - an open source ECG delineation toolbox for MATLAB *SoftwareX* **13** 100639
- Prifti E et al 2021 Deep learning analysis of electrocardiogram for risk prediction of drug-induced arrhythmias and diagnosis of long QT syndrome *Eur. Heart J.* **42** 3948–61
- Rohatgi R K, Sugrue A, Bos J M, Cannon B C, Asirvatham S J, Moir C, Owen H J, Bos K M, Kruisselbrink T and Ackerman M J 2017 Contemporary outcomes in patients with long QT syndrome *J. Am. Coll. Cardiol.* **70** 453–62
- Schwartz P J, Crotti L and Insolia R 2012 Long-QT syndrome *Circ. Arrhythm. Electrophysiol.* **5** 868–77
- Schwartz P J et al 1995 Long QT syndrome patients with mutations of the SCN5A and HERG genes have differential responses to Na⁺ channel blockade and to increases in heart rate. Implications for gene-specific therapy *Circulation* **92** 3381–6
- Schwartz P J et al 2001 Genotype-phenotype correlation in the long-QT syndrome *Circulation* **103** 89–95
- Shimizu W and Antzelevitch C 2000 Differential effects of beta-adrenergic agonists and antagonists in LQT1, LQT2 and LQT3 models of the long QT syndrome *J. Am. Coll. Cardiol.* **35** 778–86
- Srutova M, Kremen V and Lhotska L 2025 Electrocardiographic discrimination of long QT syndrome genotypes: a comparative analysis and machine learning approach *Sensors* **25** 2253
- Tan H L, Bardai A, Shimizu W, Moss A J, Schulze-Bahr E, Noda T and Wilde A A M 2006 Genotype-specific onset of arrhythmias in congenital long-QT syndrome *Circulation* **114** 2096–103
- Tardo D T, Peck M, Subbiah R N, Vandenberg J I and Hill A P 2023 The diagnostic role of T wave morphology biomarkers in congenital and acquired long QT syndrome: a systematic review *Ann. Noninvasive Electrocardiol.* **28** e13015
- Vest A N, Poian G D, Li Q, Liu C, Nemati S, Shah A J and Clifford G D 2018 An open source benchmarked toolbox for cardiovascular waveform and interval analysis *Physiol. Meas.* **39** 105004
- Zareba W and Cygankiewicz I 2008 Long QT syndrome and short QT syndrome *Prog. Cardiovasc. Dis., Sudden Cardiac Death* **51** 264–78
- Zhang L et al 2000 Spectrum of ST-T-wave patterns and repolarization parameters in congenital long-QT syndrome *Circulation* **102** 2849–55